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Abstract book

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Invasive thymoma treatment – single institution experience

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Introduction

Thymomas are malignant epithelial tumors of the thymic gland, lymphatic organ located in anterior and middle mediastinum. Thymoma classification includes: TNM staging, Surgical-pathological classification (MASAOKA) and WHO classification. Stage I-III method of choice is surgical treatment. Radiation therapy is indicated only in II (a/b) and stage III. In R1/R2 resection, adjuvant chemoradiation is required, in I-III stage. The aim of this study was to evaluate treatment modalities of patients with diagnosed thymoma.

Material and Methods

Retrospective study was conducted in Institute for pulmonary diseases of Vojvodina, which included patients with diagnosed thymoma, stage I-IV, from January 2012 to December 2021.

Results

Majority of patients were: females (65,4%), previously surgically treated (76,9%), stage III (34,6%), WHO type B1 (34,6%). In total 20 (76,9%) patients are alive. In almost all irradiated patients (91,7%) postoperative radiation (PORT) dose was relatively uniform 45Gy or 54Gy. None of the patients in I stage received PORT. All 6 patients (100%) in stage II had postoperative irradiation. Almost equal number of patients in stage III were and were not irradiated (44,4% vs 55,6%). Only one patient (25%) in stage IV received palliative dose of 20Gy/5 fr.

Conclusion

Most of the patients were surgically treated, and PORT was administered in patients' stage II and III, which is according to NCCN and ESMO guidelines.

Keywords: thymoma, treatment, radiation therapy, surgery

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